

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE TRANSVERSE DIFFUSIVITY

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ABSTRACT

A Finite Element (FE) solution is proposed for one dimensional moisture diffusion through a uni-directional composite with a regular packed fibre distribution and is found to be in general agreement with previously developed models. Random fibre distributions are developed using a hard core Gibb's process and the transverse diffusivity through them determined using FE analysis. There is found to be negligible difference between fully random and regular packed distributions. However, if high and low fibre volume fractions are distributed in layered structures the transverse diffusivity is significantly reduced.

INTRODUCTION

A critical aspect of using epoxy matrix composites in aerospace applications is their performance in 'hot-wet' environments. Epoxy resins readily absorb atmospheric moisture which results in reduced mechanical performance of the composite. In order to characterise the effects of moisture and moisture gradient within an epoxy matrix composite, the parameters of material diffusivity and maximum moisture content must be known. These parameters will vary with environmental conditions, fibre volume fraction (V_f) and sample dimensions. This paper presents the results of experimental and theoretical investigations into the effect of sample fibre volume fraction and the distribution of fibres within that fraction, on the transverse diffusivity of epoxy matrix composites.

Diffusion is one of several physical phenomena well described by a form of elliptic (in the steady state condition) or parabolic (in the non-steady-state condition) partial-differential equation. The diffusion equation, as proposed by Fick [1], with c representing moisture concentration at a specific cartesian point (x,y,z) and time (t) and D the material's diffusivity, is:

$$\frac{\partial c(x,y,z,t)}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 c(x,y,z,t) \quad (1)$$

Several authors [2,3,4] have reported on the general compliance of epoxy resins to this equation. These references suggest that Eqn. (1) may be assumed to be an adequate approximation of the sorption characteristics of most epoxy resin systems. With this

assumption made, analogies between Fick's equation and such phenomena as heat and electrical conduction or potential and groundwater flow may be made to find theoretical approximations for diffusivity along principal axes.

Figure 1: Principal Diffusion Axes

Figure 2: Regular Array Unit Cells

Of the many models used analogously to predict composite diffusivity perpendicular to the fibres the more commonly utilised include those based on combinations of thermal resistance [5], material shear properties [6], or electrical conductivity [3]. Additionally, numerical methods such as alternating direction implicit integration [7] or Finite Element Analysis (FEA) [8] have been utilised to solve Eqn. (1) directly.

TRANSVERSE DIFFUSIVITY THROUGH A REGULAR FIBRE DISTRIBUTION

The moisture flux (F) in a particular direction n may be written as:

$$F_n = -D_n \frac{\partial C}{\partial n} \tag{2}$$

An uni-directional fibre-reinforced composite material has three principal diffusion axes as shown in Fig. 1. The fibres and matrix are considered to be homogeneous and isotropic thus making the composite diffusivities perpendicular to the fibres equivalent. Fick's law for the steady state condition with no X-axis concentration gradient then reduces to a two dimensional elliptic equation:

$$D_t \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \right) = 0 \tag{3}$$

where D_t represents the transverse diffusivity of the composite. The distribution of fibres within a composite is commonly assumed to be either a tetragonal or hexagonal packed array [5]. The unit cells of these regular arrays are shown in Fig. 2, with the one dimensional diffusion steady state boundary conditions shown in Table 1. Combining Eqn. (3) and the law of conservation of mass within a control volume, the volume average flux ($[F]_V$) within each of the cells may then be written as:

$$[F_y]_{V_{hexagonal}} = -D_t \frac{C}{\sqrt{3}(r + e)} \quad [F_y]_{V_{tetragonal}} = -D_t \frac{C}{(r + e)} \tag{4}$$

To homogenise the fibre and matrix contributions into a composite relation the flux within the cells is integrated to produce an alternative expression for the volume average flux:

$$[F_y] = \frac{1}{V} \int_V (F_{y_m} + F_{y_f}) dV = \frac{1}{V} \left(\int_{V_m} D_m \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_m dV_m + \int_{V_f} D_f \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_f dV_f \right) \tag{5}$$

where the subscripts f and m represent the fibre and matrix properties respectively.

Table 1: Boundary Conditions for Regular Packed Array Unit Cells

Parameter	Hexagonal Unit Cell		Tetragonal Unit Cell	
Concentration (c :g/m ³)	at $y=0$ at $y=\sqrt{3}(r+e)$	$c=0$ $c=C$	at $y=0$ at $y=(r+e)$	$c=0$ $c=C$
Concentration Gradient ($\partial c/\partial n$:g/m ⁴)	at $z=0$ & $(r+e)$ on fibre/matrix boundary	$\partial c/\partial z=0$ $\partial c/\partial \bar{n}=0$	at $z=0$ & $(r+e)$ on fibre/matrix boundary	$\partial c/\partial z=0$ $\partial c/\partial \bar{n}=0$

where \bar{n} indicates a direction normal to the surface of the fibre

For composites comprised of glass or graphite fibres the contribution of the fibre to the diffusivity of the unit cell may be neglected as they do not absorb moisture. This allows Eqn. (4) and Eqn. (5) to be combined to give:

$$\frac{D_t}{D_m} = \frac{\int v_m \left(\frac{\partial c}{\partial y} \right)_m dV_m}{C(r+e)} \quad (6)$$

for both unit cells. The solution to the volume integral is obtained through use of FEA, utilising eight node isoparametric quadrilateral elements to model the composite matrix, and applying the boundary conditions listed in Table 1. The result of solving Eqn. (6) at varying unit cell volume fractions is shown in Fig. 3 (compared with previous models) and Fig. 4 (compared with experimental data from various sources).

Figure 3: Tetragonal Model Comparison

Figure 4: Experimental Comparison

EXPERIMENTAL TRANSVERSE DIFFUSIVITY

As part of an investigation into the effect of substrate moisture on adhesive bond integrity, Ciba-Geigy Fibredux® 924 resin and T800/924 prepreg samples have been subjected to a variety of environmental conditions and their moisture absorption from dry recorded against time. The environmental humidity conditions are maintained by use of saturated salt solutions placed within airtight containers, in which the samples are stored during uptake. By fitting Eqn. (1) to the recorded moisture uptake data, sample bulk diffusivity may be calculated. Corrections for edge diffusion have been made through the method proposed by Shen and Springer [5]. The calculated D_t/D_m values are shown in Fig. 4 with the experimental results of other authors.

TRANSVERSE DIFFUSIVITY THROUGH A RANDOM FIBRE DISTRIBUTION

Several physical parameters affect the transverse diffusivity of fibre reinforced composites. The effect of macroscopic fibre volume fraction has been shown in the previous section while other factors such as stress [9], void content [3], interphase [3], fibre shape [10] and resin rich regions [8] have been studied by other workers.

Examination of cross-sections of uni-directional fibre reinforced composites typically show microscopic variations in the fibre volume fraction. This leads to regions of higher-than-average and lower-than-average localised fibre volume fraction. Kondo and Taki attempted to account for such irregularity by including a region of zero volume fraction within a region of higher-than-average volume fraction. This technique while valid if only considering resin rich regions indispersed within regular packed fibre arrays fails to account for irregular packed fibre arrays. A test case of applying an upper surface concentration less than both the matrix and homogenised composite maximum moisture content suggests that Kondo and Taki's model is incorrect and that the FE model (and models in similar agreement) are a better approximation for the theoretical composite diffusivity.

It is necessary to determine the effect of irregular fibre packing to define fully the physical parameters that affect the sorption characteristics of uni-directional composites. Firstly an assessment of the irregularity is required. Several samples of the T800/924 cured samples used for the experimental phase of this work were cut, polished and their cross-sections photo-imaged using a Confocal Laser Scanning Microscope. These images were then subdivided into hexagonal and tetragonal unit cells corresponding to the average fibre radius. The subdivided unit cells of the samples were then analysed to determine the fibre volume fraction of each cell. Typically the images provided a unit cell grid of approximately 20×25 (for tetragonal unit cells). Since the aim was to determine the diffusivity ratio D_t/D_m for samples of all bulk fibre volume fractions, information on the distribution of unit cell volume fraction was required.

Theoretical unit cell volume fraction distribution was determined from a hard-core Gibb's process simulated in a manner similar to Ripley [11]. A control volume of known bulk volume fraction is constructed using an hexagonal regular packed fibre array (see Fig. 5). The hexagonal array is chosen as a starting array due to the higher probability of such an array existing especially at higher bulk fibre volume fractions [7]. From this array random fibres are removed and replaced randomly within the confines of the control volume (edges permitted to overlap - see Fig. 6). The significant difference between Ripley's method and that employed in the process utilised for this research is the region into which the replacement fibre may be randomly inserted. Ripley allows the fibre to take any position within the control volume whereas we use a square region, centred on the original position,

of side length $r.(1-V_f)$ to reduce processing time. By gradually increasing the number of times the regular array was manipulated using the reduced recipient area the general shape of the distribution curve was found to remain reasonably constant after approximately twelve iterations. With the random distribution created the individual unit cell fibre volume fractions could be determined and a theoretical distribution determined. The theoretical distributions and their comparison to the experimental results can be seen in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 respectively.

Figure 5: Initial Regular Packed Hexagonal Array of known V_f

Figure 6: Randomly distributed fibre array of known Bulk V_f

To assess the effect of the microscopic variation in V_f throughout a sample, a finite element model of mesh dimensions identical to the computer generated distribution grid was developed. The mesh was constructed of four node quadratic elements whose diffusivities were determined from their respective V_f values (allocated according to the computer generated distribution) and the corresponding regular fibre distribution unit cell model. The analysis shows that the randomly distributed model performs identically (within the accuracy of the calculations) to that of a sample of regular packed fibres of equivalent mean V_f . This suggests that it is valid to use the ideal model wherever random packing may be assumed and eliminates fibre packing variation as an explanation for differences between theoretical and experimental results.

Figure 7: Distribution of unit cell V_f at various values of bulk control volume V_f :
 (a) Hexagonal unit cell and (b) Tetragonal unit cell

Whilst the random distribution of fibres in a matrix does not appear to affect the transverse diffusivity, any non-random packing such as definite resin rich layers will do. In prepreg composites a resin rich layer often forms between the plies during consolidation. This resin rich layer is often quite continuous and has been observed within the samples used in this research to be in the order of $\frac{1}{2}$ - 3 fibre diameters wide. This represents a significant

portion of the thickness of an individual ply (worst-case 10-15%). Fig. 9 shows a schematic representation of this resin layer formed between two plies of randomly distributed fibres with a fibre volume fraction (V_{pf}) greater than that of the bulk composite.

Figure 8: Variation in unit cell V_f for theoretical and experimental fibre distributions (a) Hexagonal unit cell - Bulk $V_f \approx 0.60$ and (b) Tetragonal Unit Cell - Bulk $V_f \approx 0.65$

Again this model may be solved using FEA or more simply by acceptance of the accuracy of the regular packed models and consideration of flux continuity within the cell described by Fig. 9. The diffusivity of plies 1 and 2 are assumed equivalent (D_p) and the diffusivity of the resin layer is obviously that of the matrix (D_m). In the steady state the concentration step from the top surface to the top edge of the resin layer must be equal to the step from the lower resin edge to the bottom cell surface, i.e.:

Figure 9: Resin Rich Layer Unit Cell

$$C - C_1 = C_2 \tag{7}$$

Also the flux across any horizontal surface must be equal:

$$\left(\frac{C - C_1}{h} \right) D_p = \left(\frac{C_1 - C_2}{l} \right) D_m \tag{8}$$

Eqn. (6) may be re-written for the resin layer situation as:

$$D_t = \frac{2 \cdot \int_0^h D_p \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_p dy + \int_h^{h+l} D_m \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_m dy}{C} = \frac{2 \cdot (C - C_1) D_p + (C_1 - C_2) D_m}{C} \tag{9}$$

Solving Eqn.'s (7) through (9), where D_p is known from the regular array models, allows the net transverse diffusivity of the multi-ply cell to be calculated for a corresponding bulk composite V_f . The bulk V_f is related to V_{pf} by the relationship V_f (bulk) = $V_{pf} \cdot (1-R)$, where $R=1/(2h+1)$. The result of using a random distribution of fibres within the plies (and FEA) produces the same values of D_t/D_m as the simplified approach (as expected) which are shown in Fig.'s 10 and 11. A resin layer of $R=0.1$ thickness can be seen to reduce the transverse diffusivity from 0.252 to 0.219 (13%) for the hexagonal model and from 0.242 to 0.195 (19%) for the tetragonal model.

Figure 10: Effect of Resin Layer on Diffusivity - Hexagonal Array Model

Figure 11: Effect of Resin Layer on Diffusivity - Tetragonal Array Model

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The simple one dimensional solution of Fick's law using FEA results in a model which is quite comparable to that of other techniques and analogies. The choice of unit cell affects the predicted transverse diffusivity only at high (> 0.55) fibre volume fractions. Fig. 4 shows that the spread in experimental data is quite significant. If the results of references [3] and [8] are ignored however, the simple model provides an excellent first approximation to the transverse diffusivity of a fibre reinforced composite.

The hard core Gibb's process used to develop random fibre distributions shows good agreement with the experimentally measured distribution. The only significant difference between the computer generated and experimentally measured data, that may cause errors within a model utilising the computer generated distribution, is that the experimental data shows higher percentages of very-low and very-high fibre volume fraction unit cells than the hard core process. This may be a result of the external pressure applied to the samples during consolidation and cure, forcing fibres against each other, which then continue to move together until the matrix gels. This would generate localised regions of very high V_f and, consequently, regions of lower than average V_f . While the deviation from the computer generated distribution is noted, the effect of these extreme regions of V_f is thought to be negligible provided they are distributed throughout a sample. With this caveat, the assumption may be made that the transverse diffusivity through random or regular fibre distributions will be effectively the same for a given bulk V_f .

However, the equivalence between regular and random distributions is lost if the completeness of the random array deteriorates. Should the regions of high V_f , mentioned in the previous paragraph, group together into distinct layers they may act as a low porosity filter for the resin, effectively trapping the resin internally in lower volume fraction or even pure resin layers. While the fibres are still distributed in regions of local randomness (see Fig. 9) the diffusivity of the bulk composite is reduced (see Fig. 10 and Fig. 11). For a given bulk V_f the ply regions must be at higher-than-average V_f with a correspondingly lower diffusivity, effectively slowing the net diffusion process within the composite. The effect of the resin layer may be used to account, in part, for the differences between experimental results and the simple regular array model. Comparing Fig. 4 with Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 shows that even a small resin layer between plies would bring the model results into agreement with the significant portion of experimental data. This does leave other experimental results even further in disagreement with the model, but other parameters such as those mentioned in references [3,8,9&10] may provide explanation for such deviations.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of bulk composite fibre volume fraction on the ratio of transverse composite diffusivity to matrix diffusivity has been investigated using FEA to solve Fick's law in one dimension. The analysis considered regular packed fibre distributions as well as random fibre distributions. The diffusivity ratio was found to be unaffected by use of a random fibre distribution suggesting that the regular array model is adequate provided the fibres may be considered to be in a truly random distribution. If however, a resin layer is formed between two layers of randomly distributed fibres, a reduction in bulk composite diffusivity is predicted for a given bulk composite fibre volume fraction. This effect may be used to account, in part, for the variation between the experimental and regular array model results.

REFERENCES

1. Fick A., *Annln Phys*, Vol. 170, 1855, p 59.
2. Shirrell C.D., **Diffusion of Water Vapour in Graphite/Epoxy Composites**, Advanced Composite Materials - Environmental Effects, ASTM STP 658, J.R. Vinson Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1978, pp 21-42.
3. Woo M. & Piggott M.R., **Water Absorption of Resins and Composites: IV. Water Transport in Fibre Reinforced Plastics**, Journal of Composites Technology & Research, Vol. 10 No.1, Spring 1988, pp 20-24.
4. McKague E.L. Jnr., Reynolds J.D. & Halkias J.E., **Moisture Diffusion in Fibre Reinforced Plastics**, Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology, Transactions of the ASME, Jan 1976, pp 92-95.
5. Shen C.H. & Springer G.S., **Moisture Absorbtion and Desorption of Composite Materials**, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 10, Jan 1976, pp 2-20.
6. Halpin J. & Tsai S., **Effects of Environmental Factors on Composite Materials**, AFML-TR 67-423, 1969.
7. Augl J.M. & Berger A.E., **The effect of Moisture on Carbon Fibre Reinforced Composites I: Diffusion**, Naval Surface Weapons Centre, NSWC/WOL TR 76-7, 27 September 1976.
8. Kondo K. & Taki T., **Moisture Diffusivity of Unidirectional Composites**, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 16, 1982, pp 82-93.
9. Neumann S. & Marom G., **Stress Dependence of the Coefficient of Moisture Diffusion in Composite Materials**, Polymer Composites, Vol. 6, Jan 1985, pp 9-12.
10. Aditya P.K. & Sinha P.K., **Effects of Fibre Shapes on Moisture Diffusion Coefficients**, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, Vol. 12, Sep 1993, pp 973-986.
11. Ripley B.D., **Simulating Spatial Patterns: Dependent Samples from a Multivariate Density**, Applied Statistics, Vol 28, 1979, pp 109-112.
12. Verpoest I. & Springer G.S., **Moisture Absorption Characteristics of Aramid-Epoxy Composites**, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, Vol. 7, Jan 1988, pp 2-22.
13. Tang J. & Springer G.S., **Effects of Cure and Moisture on the Properties of Fiberite 976 Resin**, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, Jan 1988, pp 2-14.
14. DeIasi R. & Whiteside J.B., **Effect of Moisture on Epoxy Resins and Composites**, Advanced Composite Materials - Environmental Effects, ASTM STP 658, J.R. Vinson Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1978, pp 2-20.